

LEADER BEHAVIOR OF SCHOOL HEADS AND ORGANIZATIONAL AGILITY OF TEACHERS

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Abstract: This study aimed to determine which domain of information and communication technology competency of teachers best influences regulation of academic motivation of students. This study utilized the non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive technique involving teachers in Sarangani District, Davao Occidental Division, Philippines. The study was conducted on the second semester of school year 2020-2021. Research instruments on information and communication technology competency of teachers and regulation of academic motivation of students were used as source of data. Using mean, pearson-r, and regression as statistical tools to treat the data, the study showed the following results: the level of information and communication technology competency of teachers is high, the level of regulation of academic motivation of students is high, there is significance on the relationship between information and communication technology competency of teachers and regulation of academic motivation of students, the indicators of information and communication technology competency of teachers that best influences regulation of academic motivation of students which is social and ethical competency.

Keywords: information and communication technology competency of teachers, regulation of academic motivation of students, educational management.

I. INTRODUCTION

The teaching and learning environment is constantly changing to cope with the demands of time. It is also challenged by a number of variables that greatly impact teacher performance in the delivery of work functions. With the continuous change that is taking place in the educational system, teachers need a great deal of organizational agility to keep abreast with the needs of work environment (Bahrami, Kiani, Montazeralfaraj, Zadeh & Zadeh, 2016).

Organizational agility is the ability of the teachers to respond efficiently to the challenge in the workplace. Teachers need considerable level of attentiveness to thrive in the workplace that demands more time and work quality. It is imperative that school heads need to assist teachers to cope with the demands by manifesting a substantial leadership behavior that encourages teachers to work efficiently Omidvar, Zahed, Moeinikia & Khaleghkhah, 2021).

Teachers in different schools do not exhibit the necessary organizational agility. Many among them do not exhibit ability to manage their tasks as the school transitioned to remote learning. These teachers find the challenges in the work as primary cause of burnout. More so, these teachers do not embrace the culture of change that is taking place in the educational learning environment making them carry the burden in delivering the function of teaching the students (Menon & Suresh, 2020).

In the local context, there are teachers who turn down innovations and strategies that will help them lessen the burden in their work. These teachers do not allow some strategies to intervene in their work practice for fear that they will be spending more time to familiarize the strategy or for anticipating that they need to learn new concepts in order to utilize the strategies in the workplace.

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The problem-situations mentioned are the experiences of the teachers on organizational agility. The need to address the problem will ensure greater learning opportunities for the students. Hence, the researcher is prompted to conduct this study to address the knowledge gap in terms of finding relevant evidence in the local context regarding leader behavior of the school heads and organizational agility of the teachers as the researcher has rarely come across with the same study on the same topic in the local setting.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE**Statement of the Problem**

This study aims to find out which domain of leader behavior of school heads best influences organizational agility of teachers. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following objectives:

1. To describe the level of leader behavior of school heads in terms of:

- 1.1. visualizing Greatness;
- 1.2. empowering;
- 1.3. social navigation;
- 1.4. communicating for meaning;
- 1.5. managing one's self, and
- 1.6. care and recognition.

2. To ascertain the level of organizational agility of teachers in terms of:

- 2.1 dynamic strategy;
- 2.2 perceiving;
- 2.3 testing, and
- 2.4 implementing.

3. To determine the significant relationship between leader behavior of school heads best and organizational agility of teachers.

4. To determine which domains of leader behavior of school heads best influences organizational agility of teachers.

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis will be treated at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between leader behavior of school heads best and organizational agility of teachers.
2. No domain of leader behavior of school heads best influences organizational agility of teachers.

III. METHODOLOGY**Research Design**

This study utilized a quantitative correlational design is a type of non-experimental research design used to determine whether and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more quantifiable variables. This study will find out the significance of the relationship between leader behavior of school heads and organizational agility of teachers.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis of data.

Mean. This was used to determine the level of leader behavior of school heads best and organizational agility of teachers.

Pearson-r. This was used to determine the relationship between leader behavior of school heads best and organizational agility of teachers.

Regression. This was used to determine which domains of leader behavior of school heads best influences organizational agility of teachers.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Leader Behavior of School Heads

Presented in Table 1 is the level of *Leader Behavior of School Heads* with the overall mean of 4.27 with a descriptive equivalent of *very high* indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes manifested. The overall mean was the results obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which is appended in this study. Among the enumerated indicators, *Visualizing Greatness* obtained the highest mean score of 4.43 or very high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows:

Table 1. Leader Behavior of School Heads

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Visualizing Greatness	0.58	4.43	Very High
Empowering	0.65	4.28	Very High
Social Navigation	0.53	4.23	Very High
Communicating for Meaning	0.56	4.25	Very High
Managing One’s Self	0.62	4.21	Very High
Care and Recognition	0.56	4.26	Very High
Overall	0.49	4.27	Very High

Has visions and dreams of what can be, Has a desire to make something happen, Has a clear image of the future, Expresses enthusiasm for his/her future, and Experiments, innovates, and takes risks to find new or better ways.

The indicator *Empowering* obtained the highest mean of 4.28 with a descriptive rating of very high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: Let people (empowers them to) do what they believe is right, Gets people involved in decisions that affect, Creates in others a sense of ownership in the organization, Enlists the support and assistance of others who have a stake in the vision, and Involves others who must live with the results.

Care and Recognition obtained a mean score of 4.26 or very high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: Publicizes peoples' successes to all employees, Celebrates team accomplishments regularly, Genuinely cares about others, and Celebrates victories.

The indicator *Communicating for Meaning* obtained a mean score of 4.25 or very high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: Explains why she/he is doing what she/he is doing, Knows his/her audience when speaking to them, Talks about the principles or values behind decisions that are made, Communicates in ways that inspire and motivate others, and Takes the time needed to explain fully what he/she is thinking.

Managing One’s Self obtained a mean score of 4.21 or very high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: Has a sense of self-determination and self-confidence, Keeps his/her own level of energy up high, Believes anything can be done; has a "can do" attitude, Is a model of persistence and perseverance, and Maintains focus and constancy of purpose.

Level of Organizational Agility of Teachers

Presented in Table 2 is the level of *Organizational Agility of Teachers*. Computations revealed an overall mean score of 4.55 or *very high*, indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes manifested. The overall mean was the results obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which is appended in this study.

Among the enumerated indicators, *Perceiving* obtained a mean score of 4.58 or very high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: spends a lot of time thinking about the future, puts as many employees as possible in contact with the external environment, especially with customers, allows information to flow freely from the outside to units and groups where it is most valuable, shares financial and business

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strategy information with all employees, and has formal mechanisms to connect senior management with people at all levels of the organization

Implementing obtained a mean score of 4.35 or very high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: considers the ability to change a strength of the organization, has a well-developed change capability, rewards seniority more than performance, pays for skills and knowledge that contribute to performance, and encourages managers to develop the leadership skills of their direct reports.

Dynamic Strategy obtained a mean score of 4.26 or very high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: has a unifying purpose or mission other than profitability and

Table II. Organizational Agility of Teachers

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Dynamic Strategy	0.84	4.26	Very High
Perceiving	0.81	4.58	Very High
Testing	0.83	4.24	Very High
Implementing	0.90	4.35	Very High
Overall	0.78	4.35	Very High

growth, develops strategies with flexibility in mind, has a culture that embraces change as normal, and has core values that reflect a change-ready organization

The indicator *Testing* obtained a mean score of 4.24 or very high. As presented in the appended table, the mean ratings of the following items under this indicator were as follows: encourages innovation, has enough budget “slack” so that people can develop new products or better ways of working together, has flexible budgets that respond to marketplace changes, is capable of shifting its structure quickly to address new opportunities, and regularly reviews learnings from change efforts

Significance on the relationship between Leader Behavior of School Heads and Organizational Agility of Teachers

Illustrated in Table 3 were the results of the test of relationship between the variables involved in the study. The overall correlation had a computed r- value of 0.326 with a probability value of 0.03 which is significant at 0.05 level. Doing an in-depth analysis, it could be gleaned that the indicators of *Leader Behavior of School Heads* and *Organizational Agility of Teachers* revealed a computed r-value ranging from .326 to .003 with probability values of 0.01 which is lesser than .05 level of significance. The significant relationship between the two variables is an indication that the increase in the level of *Leader Behavior of School Heads* led to the increase in *Organizational Agility of Teachers*.

Table III. Significance of the Relationship between Leader Behavior of School Heads and Organizational Agility of Teachers

Leader Behavior of School Heads	Organizational Agility of Teachers		
	R	p-value	Remarks
Visualizing Greatness	.428	.002	Significant
Empowering	.251	.014	Significant
Social Navigation	.825	.000	Significant
Communicating for Meaning	.135	.000	Significant
Managing One’s Self	.184	.012	Significant
Care and Recognition	.384	.015	Significant
Overall	.326	.003	Significant

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

Significance of the Influence of the Domain of Leader Behavior of School Heads on Organizational Agility of Teachers

Presented in Table 4 is the regression analysis showing the predictive ability of *Leader Behavior of School Heads* on *Organizational Agility of Teachers*.

The analysis shows that when *Leader Behavior of School Heads* was regressed on *Organizational Agility of Teachers*, it generated an F-value of 58.26 with 0.01. The value of this regression is 58.26 with 0.01.

Table IV. Regression Analysis Showing the Extent of the Influence of Predictor Variables on Digital Citizenship of Teachers

Organizational Agility of Teachers				
Leader Behavior of School Heads	β (Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	t	Sig.
Constant	1.3284	0.8273	3.75	0.000
Visualizing Greatness	-0.08325	0.09371	-0.2	0.591
Empowering	0.93816	0.07382	2.61	0.001
Social Navigation	0.08273	0.06728	0.38	0.879
Communicating For Meaning	-0.08273	0.08265	-0.2	0.591
Managing One’s Self	0.7184	0.06892	2.65	0.001
Care And Recognition	0.09278	0.07284	0.38	0.879
R	0.245			
R²	0.825			
F	58.26			
p	0.000			

It can be stated that *Leader Behavior of School Heads* influenced *Organizational Agility of Teachers*. Among the indicators of *Leader Behavior of School Heads* only two gave significant influence on *Organizational Agility of Teachers*, these are Managing One’s Self, $t=2.65$, $P=0.001$ and Empowering, $t=2.61$, $P=0.001$.

V. CONCLUSION

With considerations on the findings of the study, conclusions are drawn in this section. The level of leader behavior of school heads is very high, the level of organizational agility is very high, there is a significance of the relationship between leader behavior of school heads and organizational agility of teachers, and domains of leader behavior of school heads best influences organizational agility of teachers are Managing One’s Self and Empowering.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of this study revealed that the level of leader behavior of school heads is very high is very high. The researcher recommends that the District where the study is conducted in Schools Division Office of Davao Occidental may conduct training that will help improve the aspects of Managing One’s Self.

Meanwhile, the study revealed a very high level of organizational agility. The researcher recommends that the district office may provide Learning Action Cell among the teachers on the topic Testing.

The study found a significant relationship between leader behavior of school heads and organizational agility of teachers. The researcher therefore recommends that the District Office may consider the provision of trainings or activities relative to the variables under study to help the school heads and teachers enhance on the indicators which are among the lowest in the indicators of the variables under study.

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The study found that indicators of domains of leader behavior of school heads best influences organizational agility of teachers are Managing One's Self and Empowering. The researcher recommends that school heads may provide sessions in Learning Action Cell among teachers for improvement.

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